

**Energy Distribution in the associated Gravitational-wave and
Electromagnetic events of GRB170817A/GW170817.**

A Report Submitted
in Fulfilment of the Requirements
for the Degree of

MASTER OF SCIENCE
in
PHYSICS

by

ALLADA SURYA VAMSHI
(MSC22418)

to

SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION AND RESEARCH
THIRUVANANTHAPURAM - 695 551, INDIA

September 2025

Declaration of Authorship

DECLARATION

I, **ALLADA SURYA VAMSHI** (Roll No: **MSC22418**), hereby declare that this report entitled **”Energy Distribution in the associated Gravitational-wave and Electromagnetic events of GRB170817A/GW170817.”** submitted to Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Thiruvananthapuram towards the fulfillment of **Master of Science in Physics**, is an original work carried out by me under the supervision of **Dr. Shabnam Iyyani**. I have sincerely tried to uphold academic ethics and honesty. Whenever a piece of external information or statement or result is used then, that has been duly acknowledged and cited.

Thiruvananthapuram - 695 551

ALLADA SURYA VAMSHI

April 2024

Certificate

This is to certify that the work contained in this project report entitled "**Energy Distribution in the associated Gravitational-wave and Electromagnetic events of GRB170817A/GW170817.**" submitted by **ALLADA SURYA VAMSHI** (Roll No. **MSC22418**) to the Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Thiruvananthapuram towards the fulfillment of **Master of Science in Physics** has been carried out by him under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree.

Dr. Shabnam Iyyani

Project Supervisor
Department of Physics
IISER Thiruvananthapuram

ABSTRACT

Name of the student: **ALLADA SURYA VAMSHI**

Roll No: **MSC22418**

Degree for which submitted: **M.Sc.**

Department: **School of Physical Sciences**

Thesis title: **Energy Distribution in the associated Gravitational-wave and Electromagnetic events of GRB170817A/GW170817.**

Thesis supervisor: **Dr. Shabnam Iyyani**

Date of thesis submission: **April 2024**

GW170817 is a gravitational event that corresponds to the merger of binary neutron stars. The electromagnetic spectrum, from gamma rays to radio waves, is released as a result of the merging of its components. Considering the energy the binary possessed in the Gravitational Potential Energy 10 seconds before the merger as the source of these events, which was calculated as 1.4×10^{53} ergs, the energy partition into different events associated with this binary is estimated. The GRB170817A was observed off-axis by an angle of 28 degrees. From our calculation, the maximum energy released during the GRB prompt emission is in the order of 10^{52} ergs when observed on-axis, which accounts for 13 - 18 % of the total potential energy considered. The GW emission carried the energy in a similar order during the last few seconds before the merger, constituting 9 - 12% of the total energy before the merger. The energy values reported in [1][2][3] for the kilonova and afterglow accounts for around 0.7 - 1.1 % and 10 - 13 % respectively.

Keywords:

GRB170817A, GW170817, Gamma Ray Bursts, Gravitational Waves.

Contents

Declaration of Authorship	i
1 Introduction	1
2 Theory	3
2.1 Gamma Ray Bursts	3
2.1.1 Short GRB's (sGRB)	3
2.1.2 Long GRB's	3
2.1.3 Traditional Uniform Jet Model:	4
2.1.4 Structured Jet	4
2.2 Gravitational Waves	5
2.3 Kilonova	5
2.4 Afterglow	5
3 GRB170817A/GW170817	6
3.1 Observation	6
4 Analysis	9
4.1 GRB170817A	9
4.2 GW170817	10
4.3 Kilonova	12
4.4 Afterglow	14
5 Results	15
Bibliography	16

Chapter 1

Introduction

On August 17, 2017, the Fermi satellite observed a potential GRB signal, and an alert was sent. After analyzing the data for six minutes, a possible GW transient was identified[4]. The signal was clearly visible in the LIGO-Hanford detector[4]. Initially, the signal was not visible in the LIGO-Livingston due to a glitch in the equipment[4]. The GW was consistent with a BNS merger that happened less than 2 seconds before GRB170817A[5], and the LIGO-Virgo rapid-response team manually examined the data, issuing a warning suggesting that the time of the GRB was associated with a highly significant GW candidate. This was the first GW event observed along different spectrums, as it was discovered by both GWs and electromagnetic (EM) waves.[5]The GW and gamma-ray signal pinpointed the position of the sky; therefore, telescopes worldwide focused their efforts on making more observations connected to this source. Numerous significant observations were made at various electromagnetic wavelengths and neutrino fluence measurements.

At the time of the announcement for GW170817, the event had settled in sky of Australia, but it could still be seen from observatories in South Africa and Chile[5][6]. During the first few hours, the Swope telescope observed an optical transient (SSS17a) coming from the NGC 4993 galaxy[5][6]. Over the next two weeks, several ground-based telescopes and space-based observatories corroborated the preliminary observations in the ultraviolet (UV), optical (O), and near-infrared (IR)[5][6].

These studies monitored the SED, revealing that the exceptional electromagnetic counterpart was a kilonova. This finding reveals a close link between kilonovae and the BNS merger[6].

Following the kilonova, X-ray and radio observatories probed the source, recording a corresponding signal from the explosion[5][6]. These measurements revealed significant details regarding the explosion's energy production, ejected material, and merger conditions[5][6]. Neutrino observatories tried to look for high-energy neutrinos from the GW170817 area, released during a BNS merger's relativistic outflow. However, no neutrinos were identified as a result of this merger[5][6].

FIGURE 1.1: Timeline for the discovery of GW170817, GRB170817A, SSS17a/AT2017gfo, and subsequent observations.

Source: <https://www.ligo.org/science/Publication-GW170817MMA/>

Chapter 2

Theory

2.1 Gamma Ray Bursts

These small flashes of high-energy light come from events like the birth of black holes and collisions between neutron stars. These bursts last a few milliseconds to hours and can be hundreds of times brighter than an average supernova. Thus, when a GRB erupts for a short duration, it becomes the brightest source of electromagnetic radiation in the observable Universe.

2.1.1 Short GRB's (sGRB)

In 2005, astronomers determined that sGRBs can be linked with the merger of two neutron stars or by a merger and collision between a black hole and a neutron star. The merger model of sGRBs implies that neutron stars in binary systems orbit together. After a certain time, the neutron stars collide and merge. This triggers a final blast of gravitational waves, a blast of EM radiation called a kilonova and a GRB.

2.1.2 Long GRB's

Long-duration GRBs account for approximately 70% of gamma-ray events detected thus far. They are associated with the collapse of the core of a massive star, with starting masses beginning at 5 - 10 M_{\odot} . This collapse occurs when a massive star runs out of fuel for nuclear fusion and can no longer support itself against its own inward gravitational influence. As the core of this dying star collapses, the outer layers are blasted free by massive supernovas.

There are few models to explain the jet structure when we not viewing it directly. [7]” A uniform top-hat jet (the most straightforward model) is a model in which we consider that the observer is viewing from

FIGURE 2.1:
 Source: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1710/1710.05834.pdf>

a side”. The other possible explanation is a structured jet, which is concentrated on the axis but we are seeing from the off-axis, or we could have some core material (cocoon) pushed out of the way by the main jet, which emits radiation, and we are observing it.

2.1.3 Traditional Uniform Jet Model:

This model assumes a GRB jet is a cone-shaped outflow with a constant energy distribution within its core. The energy per unit solid angle $dE_K/d\Omega$ and the bulk Lorentz factor (Γ) are assumed to be constant throughout the jet’s opening angle $\theta \leq \theta_j$. This model is often called the “**top-hat**” jet structure. The top-hat model predicts the afterglow emission of a GRB by assuming the jet interacts with the surrounding medium. This interaction leads to a characteristic decline in the afterglow’s brightness over time, which can be compared to observations.

2.1.4 Structured Jet

This model proposes a detailed understanding of the jet’s non-uniform energy distribution. It explores the possibility of the jet’s higher energy density in the center decreasing toward the edges. This can be visualized as a broken power-law structure rather than a constant value. The structured jet model arises from considering the complex processes involved, such as the central engine powering the jet (black hole or magnetar) and its interaction with the surrounding stellar environment as it breaks out.

2.2 Gravitational Waves

”Gravitational waves are ‘ripples’ in space-time fabric caused by the Universe’s most violent and intense processes” [7]. ”Albert Einstein anticipated their existence in his general theory of relativity” [4]. His equations demonstrated that speeding heavy mass objects (such as neutron stars or black holes orbiting each other) will disturb space-time, which propagates as waves. These waves travel at the speed of light and provide information about their origins.

2.3 Kilonova

A kilonova is an EM radiation outflow that occurs when two NS or a NS and a stellar-mass BH collide and merge.

When such an event occurs, a tremendous quantity of matter is expelled from the neutron stars. This ejected matter is rich in neutral particles known as neutrons, and since the density is so great near the core, heavy elements develop there. These include gold, platinum, and radioactive elements such as uranium and iodine.

The released material produces an electromagnetic light known as a kilonova. It appears in the sky as a flash of light that peaks and then diminishes before completely disappearing, suggesting that it is transient.

2.4 Afterglow

When a jet is released from the BNS, it moves quickly. However, as it propagates, the jet interacts with the cosmic medium. This has two results. For starters, the jet begins to spread, allowing us to view it from any angle, even when we are off-axis. The jet also conveys energy to the matter, which begins to emit energy over the electromagnetic spectrum, primarily in the X-ray, radial, and optical wavelengths. This is known as the afterglow. The main feature of afterglow is that it can last over several days or even years, unlike GRB and kilonova. So we can observe and simulate the afterglow over time to determine the jet’s starting energy.

Chapter 3

GRB170817A/GW170817

Binary Neutron Star (BNS) systems and NS-BH mergers contain matter associated with them. So, they are the events that can emit energy in both the Gravitational Waves and Electromagnetic Spectrum. A few cases of Binary Black hole mergers can also be a source for GRBs when there is a comparable mass difference between them. While the GRB emitted from the BNS/NS-BH system originates from the core matter, BBH-powered GRBs come out when the matter in the accretion disk heats up at the final stages of the merger.

As stated in the previous chapter, Long GRBs originate from a Supernova of Type Ibc and sGRB from the BNS/NS-BH system. So, GW170817 and GRB170817A originating from the same source can imply some population of short GRBs originate from BNS mergers.

3.1 Observation

”On August 17, 2017, the LIGO has seen a strange signal among the strain data of the O2 run” [4]. ”The O2 phase started on November 30, 2016, and lasted till August 25, 2017” [4]. This is the second observational run, while the first one, O1 started on September 12, 2015, and ended on January 19, 2016. At the end of the O2, [4], a signal resembling the waveform template generated from the Post-Newtonian model corresponding to a Binary Neutron Star (BNS) merger was observed.

Using the Bayesian analysis and imposing the constraints from General Relativity and Neutron star astrophysics, the parameters like mass, radius, and spins of the components are obtained [4]. In the case of GW170817, as mentioned earlier, the event is not aligned with our line sight [4]. Due to this, the spins of the components cannot be constrained. So, the authors of [4] have assumed two possible limits for the spins. [4]”The assumed two spin priors, mainly $\chi \leq 0.89$ (high spin) and $\chi \leq 0.5$ (low spin), lead to different masses of the binary objects”. [4] ”For the high-spin prior, the estimated mass of NS are m_1

$\epsilon \in (1.36, 2.26) M_{\odot}$ and $m_2 \in (0.86, 1.36) M_{\odot}$ while for a low-spin, $m_1 \in (1.36, 1.6) M_{\odot}$ and $m_2 \in (1.17, 1.36) M_{\odot}$. From the analysis of the Gravitational-wave observation GW170817, the location of the BNS system to our line of sight is 28° [4]. The estimated value of the luminosity of the jet is in the orders of 10^{45} erg/s, and energy is 10^{46} ergs[7]. Compared to the previously observed sGRBs, these values are a few orders less approximately by 3.

After the event was observed and localized, a trigger was sent to all the observatories. In the Electromagnetic spectrum, another transient called kilonova was observed[1]. The source for this transient can be the matter ejected from the system called Dynamical ejecta. The dynamical ejecta has significant fractions of the speed of light. This matter is rich in r-process elements[1]. r-process is the mechanism by which iron (Fe) or its nearby elements rapidly capture neutrons (which are highly concentrated at the core of a neutron star and abundantly available). After a certain stage, the nucleus becomes unstable and undergoes β decay, releasing high-energy photons[1]. Each of these priors have different ejecta mass ranging from 10^{-3} to $10^{-1} M_{\odot}$, $10^{-1} M_{\odot}$ corresponding to the high-spin prior[1].

As the jet propagates, it starts to interact with the surrounding matter. The particles in the jet have a tremendous amount of energy. During the interaction, some of the energy is imparted to the surrounding medium, which causes the jet to lose energy and slow down, thereby causing the jet to start to spread. The energy transferred to the particles in the surrounding medium emits radiation in the EM spectrum, which is observed as afterglow[3]

FIGURE 3.1: LIGO-Hanford, LIGO-Livingston, and Virgo detectors detected the gravitational wave event GW170817, as seen in time-frequency representations.

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.119.161101>

Chapter 4

Analysis

4.1 GRB170817A

The data for the analysis of the GRB was obtained from the HEASARC Fermi Catalog. We plotted light curves for the 3 NaI (Sodium Iodide) detectors and one BgO detector to determine the source interval. In the light curve, a sudden rise in counts was observed at -1s, marking the GRB's beginning. The count to settle in with the background took four seconds. This is not the duration of the GRB. For categorizing a GRB as short or long, the T90 is the time in which ninety percent of the total Energy is emitted. The GRB170817A falls under the category of the short GRB whose T90 is 1.77 seconds[7].

Now that the source interval is fixed (-1 to 4s), we moved on to the spectral fitting of the data. For the NaI detectors, we have considered the energy range to be 80 - 600 keV; for the bgo, it is assumed to be 250 keV - 30MeV. Different models are used in the fitting, like Band, Black body, Power Law, Broken Power Law, and Cut-off Power Law, which all yielded the Luminosity and Energy of the same order with a slight variation in the second significant digit other than the Blackbody and Cut-off Power Law models. So, we have discarded these models for further analysis. Through the successful models, we have observed Luminosity in the order of 10^{45} erg/s and the Energy in 10^{46} erg, which agrees with the values presented in [7].

As mentioned in the previous sections, this GRB is observed off-axis with a viewing angle of 28° [4]. So, we need to estimate the actual values of Luminosity and Energy. To do this, the assumptions are as follows: the jet is in the form of a power-law structured jet rather than a top-hat model, and we are observing the declining side of the jet. The other case can be where the jet had a Gaussian structure. For the on-axis correction when it is a structured jet[8],

$$L_{\text{iso}}(\theta) = L_{\text{iso},0} \left(1 + \frac{\theta}{\theta_j}\right)^k, E_{\text{iso}}(\theta) = E_{\text{iso},0} \left(1 + \frac{\theta}{\theta_j}\right)^k, \quad (4.1)$$

FIGURE 4.1: In the top panel, the light curve is plotted by merging the three NaI detectors, which give observable signals. The energies considered are from 8 KeV - 800 KeV. In the bottom panel, the light curve of the BgO detector is plotted.

Gaussian structured jet[8], i.e.,

$$E_{\text{iso}}(\theta) = E_{\text{iso},0} \exp\left(-\frac{\theta^2}{2\theta_j^2}\right), \quad (4.2)$$

Here, $L_{\text{iso}}(\theta)$, $E_{\text{iso}}(\theta)$ are the measured Luminosity and Energy at an angle θ which for our GRB is 28 degrees[8] and $L_{\text{iso},0}$, $E_{\text{iso},0}$ are the values which are observed if the viewer had been on axis. θ_j corresponds to the opening angle of the jet, which typically ranges from 5 - 12 degrees[8]. We have assumed it to be 5 degrees. k indicates the power law index of the decreasing function and can range from 4.5 to 6 according to [8]. Post these assumptions and calculations, the Luminosity is in the order of 10^{49} erg/s and Energy to be 10^{50} erg. If the jet structure is assumed to be Gaussian, the Energy is in the orders of a few 2.1×10^{52} erg.

4.2 GW170817

From the detectors that observe the Gravitational waves, strain is measured. The strain data is then plotted using the gwpy library to observe the signal's frequency change as time passes. Approximately 3s before the merger time, a sharp increase in frequency is observed, indicating a gravitational wave associated with this event. From the curve, we can see that the frequency of the GW at this instant is below 100 Hz

FIGURE 4.2: Frequency vs Time for the merger event is shown. The merger time is occurring at 0s. The signal becomes visible from -3.5s before the merger. From this point, a clear increase in frequency is observed

and has risen steadily to 500 Hz[4].

Now, we need to estimate the Energy released as GW in the last few seconds of the observation. We employ the formula in [9] to do that.

$$P = \frac{8}{15} \frac{G^4}{c^5} \frac{m_1^2 m_2^2 (m_1 + m_2)}{a^5 (1 - e^2)^5} (1 + e \cos \psi)^4 \times [12(1 + e \cos \psi)^2 + e^2 \sin^2 \psi].$$

We reduce this formula for the simplest case of circular orbit where $e=0$.

$$P = (32/5) * (G^4/c^5) * (m_1 * m_2)^2 * (m_1 + m_2)^{-1/3} * (\pi f_{GW})^{10/3}$$

Power is the amount of Energy transferred or converted per unit of time. This implies that $P = dE/dt$, which, when integrated over the required time duration, gives us the Energy radiated in that duration. For this specific situation, we consider our time duration to be the last 10 seconds before the merger, which means the integration is done from -10 seconds to 0 seconds. The evolution of frequency with time is necessary to continue with the integration. From the plot above, we can see discrete values of frequencies at different time stamps. On summing them, we obtained the Energy released as GW in the 1.25×10^{52} ergs range.

To estimate the potential Energy stored in the inspiral phase, we first fixed the time from which the detectable GW increases steadily in frequency. This time, it is nearly 3s before the merger. So that means the Gravitational Potential Energy at this instant will power the rest of the phenomenon like GW, GRB,

Kilonova, and Afterglow. Post-Newtonian estimation gives the formula to calculate the orbital separation and the Energy provided by the orbital frequency. The orbital frequency is related to Gravitational-wave frequency as $f_{GW} = 2 \times f_{orb}$ [10]. The orbital frequency can be calculated since we know the frequency of the emitted GW from the GW analysis.

The formulae were borrowed from [10], which explains the relation between different binary parameters. The equations are

$$\Omega^2 = \frac{Gm}{r^3} \left\{ 1 + (-3 + \nu)\gamma + \left(6 + \frac{41}{4}\nu + \nu^2 \right) \gamma^2 + \left(-10 + \left[-\frac{75707}{840} + \frac{41}{64}\pi^2 + 22 \ln \left(\frac{r}{r_0'} \right) \right] \nu + \frac{19}{2}\nu^2 + \nu^3 \right) \gamma^3 \right\}$$

$$E = -\frac{\mu c^2 x}{2} \left\{ 1 + \left(-\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{12}\nu \right) x + \left(-\frac{27}{8} + \frac{19}{8}\nu - \frac{1}{24}\nu^2 \right) x^2 + \left(-\frac{675}{64} + \left[\frac{34445}{576} - \frac{205}{96}\pi^2 \right] \nu - \frac{155}{96}\nu^2 - \frac{35}{5184}\nu^3 \right) x^3 \right\}$$

where,

$$x \equiv \left(\frac{Gm\Omega}{c^3} \right)^{2/3},$$

$$\gamma = \frac{Gm}{rc^2}$$

Ω is the orbital frequency, m is the total mass of the binary, G is the universal Gravitational constant, $\nu = (m_1 * m_2)/m^2$ and r is the separation[10]. We can calculate the separation at every instant by substituting the orbital frequency.

For the frequency of 100Hz, the separation is calculated to be around 350 km, which means the binary did not start at the late inspiral stage. So, we can safely assume that the potential Energy at this instant powers the other events. The Energy at this frequency is 1.4×10^{53} ergs.

4.3 Kilonova

The analysis for the estimation of Energy released by kilonova is not done by me; rather, I have directly taken the values from the published papers[2][1]. The LIGO-Virgo sky localization of GW170817 prompted a multi-messenger search across the electromagnetic spectrum for counterparts. Within hours, broadband observations, supported by archival data analysis, revealed an optical transient known as a kilonova[2][1], originating from neutron-rich materials freed from the system. Generally, two ejecta forms are likely to contribute to kilonovae[1][2]: dynamical ejecta created during the merger and post-merger winds produced by the remnant system, such as an accretion disc surrounding a black hole or a big neutron star.

To predict the Energy released as a kilonova, the authors made certain assumptions of [1] like

Ejecta mass and composition: It is assumed that during the binary neutron star merger, a certain amount of material (ejecta) is expelled.

The total mass of this ejecta is assumed to be in the range of 0.01 to 0.05 solar masses (approximately $2 \times 10^{30} - 1 \times 10^{31}$ kg).

This ejecta is assumed to contain a significant fraction of heavy elements, particularly lanthanides (elements with atomic numbers between 57 and 71). The assumed lanthanide fraction in the ejecta is typically between 10^{-4} and 10^{-2} (0.01% to 1%) by mass.

Radioactive heating rate: It is assumed that the Energy powering the kilonova emission comes from the radioactive decay of freshly synthesized heavy elements in the ejecta. The specific isotopes produced and their decay rates are calculated based on theoretical models of nuclear physics and the conditions present during the merger. The heating rate from these radioactive decays (primarily beta decays) is assumed to follow a specific time evolution based on the isotope distribution.

Ejecta geometry and opacity: The ejecta is assumed to have a specific geometric shape, such as spherical or ellipsoidal, which affects the emission and expansion dynamics. The opacity of the ejecta material, which determines how efficiently the radioactive heating is trapped and re-emitted as thermal radiation, is assumed based on theoretical models and the assumed composition (particularly the lanthanide fraction).

Emission mechanism and radiative transfer: The kilonova emission is assumed to be thermal radiation from the hot, expanding ejecta cloud. The emission is modeled using radiative transfer codes that simulate the diffusion and escape of radiation through the ejecta material. Assumptions are made about the emission mechanism (e.g., blackbody radiation, line emission) and the treatment of radiative transfer effects.

The steps involved in the estimation of the Energy released are:

1. Ejecta dynamics simulation
2. Nuclear heating rate calculation
3. Radiative transfer simulation
4. Synthetic light curve and spectra calculation
5. Parameter exploration and model fitting

Following the above steps, the Energy was estimated to be in the 10^{51} erg range [2]. The dynamical ejecta also carries some energy with it as matter is ejected. [7] The mass of it, when converted to Energy if it is assumed that the slow component of 0.001 solar-mass moves at 20% the speed of light [2] and the fast component of equal mass at 70% [2] is around 2.7×10^{52} ergs.

4.4 Afterglow

After a neutron-star merger, a jet forms from "the rapid accretion of ejected matter onto a compact remnant" [3] and spreads across the merger ejecta medium [3]. When a jet interacts with ejecta, it produces a structured outflow with bigger components, resulting in an accelerated ejecta cocoon [3]. The outflow profile is determined by the mass and density of the expelled material, as well as the jet's initial form. Simulations of jet propagation over merger ejecta can yield outflows with a Gaussian shape. This structure determines how the afterglow evolves. GRB 170817A's afterglow flux progressively grows until peaking between 10 and 150 days. The angular structure of the outflow [3] best accounts for this phenomenon. A structured outflow's broad angle components are a cocoon of merger ejecta [3] material propelled by an ultra-relativistic jet at its core.

The major assumptions made while modeling the afterglow are:

Ejecta properties: Assumptions are made about the mass, composition, and geometry of the ejecta material expelled during the merger. The ejecta is assumed to have a significant fraction of neutron-rich material, which is important for producing short-lived radioactive isotopes that power the afterglow emission.

Jet formation and structure: It is assumed that a collimated, relativistic jet is formed during the merger, likely powered by the accretion of material onto the remnant compact object (e.g., a black hole or a highly magnetized neutron star). Assumptions are made about the opening angle, Energy, and structure (e.g., uniform or structured) of the jet.

Jet-ejecta interaction: The afterglow emission is assumed to arise from the interaction between the relativistic jet and the surrounding ejecta material. This interaction is believed to produce shocks that accelerate particles and generate synchrotron radiation, observed as the afterglow.

Microphysics of the shocks: Assumptions are made about the microphysics of the shocks, including the fraction of Energy that goes into accelerating electrons and amplifying magnetic fields. These parameters, known as microphysics, affect the synchrotron radiation properties and the overall afterglow emission.

Radiative processes and transfer: Assumptions are made about the radiative processes responsible for the afterglow emission, such as synchrotron radiation and inverse Compton scattering. The transfer of radiation through the ejecta and the jet is modeled using radiative transfer codes, which involve additional assumptions about the opacity and geometry of the emitting regions.

Based on these assumptions, the afterglow is modeled, and the Energy released is estimated at 10^{52} erg [3].

Chapter 5

Results

The GW170817, an astonishing Binary Neutron Star merger, brought insights into many theoretical predictions. The component Neutron Stars have masses in the range of $(0.86, 1.36) M_{\odot}, (1.36, 2.26) M_{\odot}$ [7][4] considering the limits for both the spin priors simultaneously. When the system was in the final few seconds of the merger, the separation was around 300 km, and the merger accelerated to the final phase. The Gravitational Potential Energy calculated before this acceleration is 1.4×10^{53} ergs. This energy is distributed into Gravitational waves, Gamma Ray Burst, Kilonova, and Afterglow. Our calculation showed the energy released as Gravitational waves as $1.25 - 1.68 \times 10^{52}$ ergs. While estimating the GRB on-axis energy, each considered model has different values, but all fall in the same order. The maximum energy GRB emits $1.82 - 2.5 \times 10^{52}$ ergs while considering the jet structure to be Gaussian. The dynamical ejecta which powers the kilonova associated with the merger has an energy of $2.7 - 3.2 \times 10^{52}$ ergs[2]. The error in the measurement arises while assuming the model describing the kilonova, including the mass of the ejecta and its velocity[1]. The afterglow emitted by the interaction on the outflow jet with the surrounding medium[11] released energy in the range of $1.4 - 1.8 \times 10^{52}$ ergs[3][5]. So, we can say that of the system's total energy before the merger, 9 - 12 % was released as Gravitational waves. GRB constitutes around 13 - 18 %. A portion of energy dispersed as afterglow rounds up to 10 - 13 %. The dynamical ejecta takes approximately 20-23 % of the total energy. Summing up these energies, they approximate around 55 - 66 % of the energy before the merger. Although no neutrinos have been detected originating from this source, we can predict that some unaccounted energy might be emitted as neutrinos.

Bibliography

- [1] B. P. Abbott et al. Estimating the contribution of dynamical ejecta in the kilonova associated with gw170817. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 850, December 2017. URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/2041-8213/aa9478>.
- [2] Kathirgamaraju et al. Observable features of gw170817 kilonova afterglow. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 487, 2019. URL https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/link_gateway/2019MNRAS.487.3914K/doi:10.1093/mnras/stz1564.
- [3] G. P. Lamb, J. D. Lyman, A. J. Levan, N. R. Tanvir, T. Kangas, A. S. Fruchter, B. Gompertz, J. Hjorth, I. Mandel, S. R. Oates, D. Steeghs, and K. Wiersema. The Optical Afterglow of GW170817 at One Year Post-merger. , 870(2):L15, January 2019. doi: 10.3847/2041-8213/aaf96b.
- [4] B. P. Abbott et al. Gw170817: Observation of gravitational waves from a binary neutron star inspiral. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 119:161101, Oct 2017. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.119.161101. URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.119.161101>.
- [5] B. P et al Abbott. Multi-messenger observations of a binary neutron star merger. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 2017. URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/2041-8213/aa91c9>.
- [6]
- [7] LIGO Scientific Collaboration, Fermi Gamma-ray Burst Monitor Virgo Collaboration, and INTEGRAL. Gravitational waves and gamma-rays from a binary neutron star merger: Gw170817 and grb 170817a. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 848, October 2017. URL <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa920c>.
- [8] Jia Ren et al. Constraining the jet launching time of grb 170817a by utilizing the baryon loading. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 901, 2020. URL <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2009.04735.pdf>.
- [9] P. C. Peters and J. Mathews. Gravitational radiation from point masses in a keplerian orbit. *Phys. Rev.*, 131:435–440, Jul 1963. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.131.435. URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.131.435>.

-
- [10] Luc Blanchet. Gravitational Radiation from Post-Newtonian Sources and Inspiralling Compact Binaries. *Living Reviews in Relativity*, 5(1):3, April 2002. doi: 10.12942/lrr-2002-3.
- [11] Troja et al. The X-ray counterpart to the gravitational-wave event GW170817. , 551(7678):71–74, November 2017. doi: 10.1038/nature24290.